

ISic1024

I.Sicily inscription 1024

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

base

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Acrae

Place of origin (modern)

near Palazzolo Acreide

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palazzolo Acreide, Museo Iudica, inventory 2238

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140503

1. ἐπὶ Ἀριστοδάμου
2. τοῦ Σωσιβίου
3. Νύμφ[ων] Ἰέρωνος
4. μναμονεύσας
5. ἀγναῖς θεαῖς.
- 6.

Edition: PHI175422

1. ἐπὶ Ἀριστοδάμου
2. τοῦ Σωσιβίου
3. Νυμφ[ῶ]ι Ἰέρωνος
4. μναμονεύσασ α
5. ἀγναῖς θεαῖς.
- 6.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492652

EDCS 39102178

PHI 140503

PHI 175422

Bibliography

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